

Designation	Damage rating ^a	Reaction
ARC11324	6.3	S
Bahbolon	5.0	MR
B4032D-MR-1-3-1	6.5	S
CI 5662-2	6.8	S
Citanduy	3.9	MR
GH147 (M) KRAD-78	5.0	MR
GH147 (M) 30KRAD-C-PN7	6.5	S
GH147 (M) 40KRAD 89	7.4	S
IR13240-82-2-3-2-3-1	6.6	S
IR13475-7-3-2	3.7	MR
IR13458-117-2-3-2-3	5.2	MR
IR15529-253-3-2-2-2	4.1	MR
IR15529-256-1	4.3	MR
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	4.8	MR
IR17307-11-2-3-2	6.7	S
IR2035-117-3	5.3	MR
IR18350-93-2	7.7	S
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	6.1	S
IR25586-108-1-2-2-2	6.2	S
IR27325-27-3-3	4.2	MR
IR13475-7-3-2	5.1	MR
IR28154-101-3-2	2.4	R
IR29692-65-2-3	5.4	MR
IR31803-32-2	7.6	S
IR32307-107-3-22	3.3	R
IR32429-47-3-2-2	5.3	MR
IR2035-117-3	4.9	MR
IR60	5.0	MR
IR64 (IR18348-36-3-3)	3.2	R
Palman 46	5.8	S
Rathu Heenati	1.7	R
ARC6248 (resistant check)	1.9	R
TN1 (susceptible check)	8.9	S

^a Means of 40 plants.

after infestation. Individual plant damage was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Mean reaction of all plants was used to classify an accession as resistant (R, 0-3.49), moderately resistant (MR, 3.5-5.49), or susceptible (S, 5.5-9).

Four accessions scored R, 15 MR, and 12 S (see table). IR2035-117-3, which is homozygous for *Wbph 1* and *Wbph 2* and is being used as a R check at IRR1, was MR in our tests, indicating a difference in biotype at IRR1 and at PAU. Earlier, we reported that *Wbph 1* and *Wbph 2* are not effective in conferring resistance to WBPH in Punjab. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OTHER PESTS

Yield ability of rice varieties in fields infested with root-knot nematode

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We measured yields of three Thai rice varieties — RD6, Khao Dawk Mali 105, and Hahng Yi 71 — growing in fields infested with root-knot nematode

Meloidogyne graminicola Golden and Birchfield in an experiment at Ubonratchathani Rice Research Center in 1986. The varieties have been considered resistant, moderately resistant, and susceptible.

The experiment, in 4 replications, was under upland conditions in 5- × 7-m plots with 25- × 25-cm spacing. Plots

Yield of rice varieties grown in fields infested with root-knot nematode *M. graminicola*. Ubonratchathani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986.

Variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Loss (%)
	Non-treated	Treated	
RD6	3.8	4.3	11.6
Khao Dawk Mali 105	3.6	4.4	18.2
Hahng Yi 71	2.9	4.3	32.6

^aAv of 4 replications.

were fertilized with 24-24-12 kg NPK/ ha. In control plots, we applied 60 kg carbofuran 3 G/ ha; no nematocide was applied in test plots.

Yield loss was highest with Hahng Yi 71 (see table). □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Tiller growth as an index of salinity resistance

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Tiller growth as an index of salinity resistance was evaluated. Seeds of resistant and sensitive cultivars were

Effect of NaCl on the tiller growth of rice cultivars, Baroda, India.

Cultivar	Salinity index ^a	Tillers (no./plant)	Decrease (%) from control in		
			Tiller height	Fresh weight of tillers/plant	Dry weight of tillers/plant
<i>Salt-resistant</i>					
Co 43	58.8	39	14	46	50
CSC1	50.9	46	12	41	29
AU1	45.6	20	14	27	15
<i>Salt-sensitive</i>					
GR3	42.2	50	46	75	84
TKM9	23.5	35	21	46	51
Co 36	21.1	64	43	85	94
IR20	13.6	83	73	93	93
CSC2	5.2	46	7	33	34
TKM4	0.9	85	78	94	97
Mean	30.2	52	34	60	61

^aSalinity index = $\frac{\text{grain yield of treated plants}}{\text{grain yield of control}} \times 100$.

sown in earthen pots with 7 kg of soil in the screenhouse during the wet season. Salinization was imposed on 3-wk-old seedlings by adding 750 ml of NaCl solution (EC 10 dS/m) once each week. The pots were irrigated with normal

water on other days as required. Controls received only water. At 6 wk after initial salinization, the shoot system was harvested for growth measurements.

The salt-resistant cultivars AU1, Co 43, and CSC1 exhibited high salinity indices and experienced less reduction of tiller growth than the salt-sensitive cultivars (see table). □

Salt tolerance in rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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Rice is a salt-sensitive crop, yet it covers an appreciable area of moderately saline soils in Pakistan. Even though irrigation promotes leaching of salts, salt-tolerant varieties are essential for economic yields. We compared the salt tolerance of some hybrids and mutants that have

been developed with that of other salt-tolerant varieties.

Seedlings raised for 45 d under non saline conditions were transplanted at 1 seedling/hill and 20- × 20- cm spacing in concrete tanks (254 × 82 × 23 cm) filled with gravel saturated with Hoagland nutrient solution. At 1 wk after transplanting, 2 levels of root zone salinity — 2.4 dS/m (control) and 7.0 dS/m — were imposed, using NaCl, Na₂SO₄, CaCl₂, and MgCl₂ at a ratio of 4:10:5:1. Root zone salinity was checked

daily and maintained at the desired level. The plants were grown to maturity.

In general, salinity caused a marked reduction in all attributes of all genotypes except NIAB Rice-I, which showed negligible reduction (see table). NIAB Rice-I yielded highest, performing better than salt-tolerant Pokkali in number of productive tillers per plant, number of grains per panicle, panicle fertility percentage, and yield under saline conditions. □

Effect of saline (7.0 dS/m) and nonsaline (2.4 dS/m) conditions on yield and yield components of rice genotypes under gravel culture. Faisalabad Pakistan, 1987.

Genotype	Plant height (cm)		Productive tillers (no./plant)		Grains (no./panicle)		Panicle fertility (%)		Yield (g/plant)	
	Nonsaline	Saline	Nonsaline	Saline	Nonsaline	Saline	Nonsaline	Saline	Nonsaline	Saline
NIAB Rice-I	132.5	132.3	23.5	25.0	128.4	103.6	88.8	86.6	52.3	47.0
C23-3-1	74.8	72.3	26.8	20.5	134.2	122.3	86.4	81.5	38.3	30.6
RSR 1-84	145.0	107.5	28.5	21.0	152.4	82.2	92.3	71.3	45.3	14.1
Pokkali	180.3	143.0	23.3	18.5	145.0	82.0	82.6	65.4	58.0	16.6
RST24	139.5	100.0	17.8	14.0	105.3	66.2	78.0	63.9	16.8	11.8
Basmati 370	152.8	101.3	23.3	17.0	114.0	65.2	78.6	58.6	25.5	7.1
NIAB6	47.3	45.8	19.6	19.3	60.8	56.8	88.2	82.2	11.6	7.4
IR6	60.0	51.3	17.5	14.3	82.0	78.2	89.3	69.1	17.0	6.9
NIAB Rice II	98.8	86.7	25.0	18.0	82.3	67.8	51.5	46.4	14.4	8.5
Jhona 349/IR6	109.8	100.0	16.0	15.0	74.8	60.2	59.3	45.6	18.0	6.9

Salt tolerance in wild rices

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Seven wild species of *Oryza* and the African cultivated species *O. glaberrima* were evaluated for salt tolerance using water culture techniques in the phytotron glasshouse at 29/21°C (day/night) and 70% relative humidity. *O. sativa* cultivars Nona Bokra and IR28 were the tolerant and susceptible checks.

Seedlings at the 2- to 3- leaf stage were subjected to salt stress of 6,800 ppm (EC 12 dS/m) concentration by adding a 1:1 mixture of NaCl and CaCl₂

Survival of *Oryza* species at 6,800 ppm (EC 12 dS/m) salinity. IRRI, 1987.

Species	Accession no.	Genome	Seedlings tested (no.)	Seedlings that survived (no.)	Survival (%)
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	100855	AA	25	4	16
<i>O. nivara</i>	102163	AA	21	3	14
<i>O. punctata</i>	101434	BB	60	5	8
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100896	CC	88	5	6
<i>O. minuto</i>	101125	BBCC	55	7	13
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100885	CCDD	46	6	13
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100914	CCDD	28	4	14
<i>O. australiensis</i>	100882	EE	54	1	2
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	100115	FF	43	0	0
Nona Bokra (tolerant check)		AA	60	60	100
IR28 (susceptible check)		AA	60	0	0

to the nutrient solution. Salinization continued for 14 d. All species tested were susceptible to salinity during the

seedling stage (see table). Survival ranged from zero for *O. brachyantha* to 16% for *O. glaberrima*. □